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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, X
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As I have recently realized, a rather large number of known doubles will have 'poor' (>0.5 arcsec) a priori relative positions for the secondary. Although the STDDBL program will often fail in such cases, an added mesh-iteration for the secondary is found to improve the situation markedly. This note describes the modified program and gives some simulation results.

1. Introduction

The main idea of the STDDBL program is to use the 'well-known' relative position of the secondary in order to find the unknown position of the primary component. As shown in many simulations, this works well as long as the error in the relative position is less than about 0.4 arcsec. At 0.6 arcsec and above, the failure-rate quickly rises to unacceptable levels. So far, I have assumed that the large majority of known doubles will have 'good' (in this sense) relative positions, but information supplied by Prof. Dommaget has made it clear that this is too optimistic. The STDDBL-program needs modification, and here I describe a preliminary new version that solves most systems with relative position errors as large as 1.5-2 arcsec.

The simplest solution would of course be to make a true 'double search', varying the starting positions for both the primary and the secondary components independently. For each tested primary position, the whole mesh of secondary positions would have to be tried, computationally equivalent to going from a 1-D to a 2-D problem. In practice, more than 50 mesh-points may have to be tried for each component, increasing the computing times by a similar factor. Clearly, this is practicable only for a very small number of cases, and something more economical has to be found for a standard program.

The '1.5-D' solution to the problem is to make the secondary-search only at 'promising' primary-positions. For some level of primary-fit, a rather large number of secondary positions are tried, and the best one is taken as the center in subsequent secondary-searches around other good primary positions. The programming is rather straightforward, but a number of 'selection-limit' parameters have to be introduced and optimized for a representative sample of simulated systems. The computing-times are considerable (even with the new HP9000/835-system of Lund Observatory), but the 'feel' for the suitable size of these parameters will certainly be valuable when the real reductions are to be made.

2. The STDDBLS program

The 'old' STDDBL program was described in NDAC/LO/107-8. The present version starts with the same primary-search, and again a normalized fit $S_a <$

$C_1(\equiv C_{\chi_a})$ is the first branching. Instead of directly doing the 'final' solution, the program now makes a series of preliminary (weighting by diagonal of information matrix) solutions with fixed *primary* position, and with the secondary position varied. (The mesh-spacing is as for the primary-search, but the number of points tried may be different). A fit $S_s < C_2$ makes the program do a 'final' solution (with correct weighting by the whole information-matrix), and if this is unquestionably good ($S_f < C_3(\equiv C_{\chi_f})$), this is the end. Normally, however, the 'final' solution is only compared with previous ones, and the currently best one is kept in memory. The first secondary-search is done with a large mesh, but after a valid 'final' solution is obtained, the number of mesh-points is decreased, and the center is defined by the currently best solution. After all primary mesh-points are exhausted (usually without the 'follow-up'-phase, cf. NDAC/LO/107), the best-fitting solution is finally adopted.

The main problem using STDDBLS is the choice of the C_i - parameters. It is impossible to make a general optimization (because this would need thousands of parameter-choices for hundreds of systems, taking CPU-years), but it is important to understand the general trends with C_i . For C_1 , a value around 50 (20 for the systems with individual IFOV-pointing) was used in STDDBL, but sometimes a higher value may be called for. (A too low value may never engage the secondary-search, but a high one makes for a lot of unnecessary computing). For C_3 , a high value allows too many 'false' solutions, while a low one greatly increases the computing-times. The balance is delicate, as will be shown by the simulations reported below. The C_2 -parameter determines when a (time-consuming) final solution is to be tried. A high value is safe but wasteful, a too low one may lose a solution.

3. First tests of STDDBLS

The STDDBLS-program has been tested on a limited sample of simulated systems, all with $H_p=8.5$ for the primary component. Excluding some preliminary tests, I have made solutions for 40 'close' systems ($\rho=0.3-1.0$ arcsec), 40 'medium' ones ($\rho=1-3$ arcsec), 40 'wide' ones ($\rho=3-10$ arcsec) and 40 'very wide' ones ($\rho=10-30$ arcsec). In all cases, the (1-axis) position mean error was taken as 1.0 arcsec for the primary, 0.7 arcsec for the secondary (relative to the primary), giving a variety of actual primary and relative errors. The systems were uniformly distributed over the sky, and the magnitude-differences were uniformly distributed between 0 and 4 mag. In these first experiments, I used an (unnecessarily) small mesh-spacing ($g=0.5$ arcsec), and 169 primary mesh-points (catching primary position errors ϵ_p up to at least 3.4 arcsec). For the secondary-searches, I used 61(19) points (allowing relative errors ϵ_r to 2.1 arcsec).

The very wide systems were treated first, and after some testing, I arrived at an 'optimal' C_1 about 35. For C_2 , values about 1.5-2 work well, with 1.8 chosen as 'standard'. Four series of solutions were then made with different C_3 , as shown in Table 1. (The number of LS-iterations in the secondary search was also varied, and a value 4 was found optimal, as already used in the primary-searches). The 'failed' and 'false' solutions are for the 'whole' ($\epsilon_r, \Delta m$)-plane (0-2.1 arcsec, 0-4 mag), and in the dm-column is given a completeness-limit in Δm below which *all* solutions are good. Decreasing C_3 diminishes the number of false solutions, but

only at the cost of substantial computing-times.

Table 1. Number of failed and false solutions, completeness-limit in Δm , and mean CPU-time per system for 40 systems with separation 10-30 arcsec (separate IFOV-pointings) and primary position error less than 3 arcsec. The mean normalized fit S_f is about 0.85, with standard deviation 0.06.

	C3	failed	false	dm	CPU(min)
0.97	0	5	2.7	4.1	
0.94	0	3	3.6	6.0	
0.91	0	1	3.9	7.0	
0.88	0	1	3.9	9.4	
0.85	0	0	4.0	16.9	

Going then to the 'close' systems, a similar round of testing led to $C_1=100$, $C_2=2.0$. (For these systems, it was also found advantageous to increase the number of LS-iterations in the secondary-search to 6). Table 2 shows again the influence of C_3 , and it is seen to be qualitatively similar to Table 1. The two failed solutions (and many of the good ones!) are for unrealistic cases with relative position errors much larger than the separation between the stars. (They are solved correctly, however, by increasing C_1 to 150).

Table 2. Number of failed and false solutions, completeness-limit in Δm , and mean CPU-time per system for 40 systems with separation 0.3-1 arcsec (single IFOV-pointing) and primary position error less than 3 arcsec. The mean normalized fit S_f is about 1.08, with standard deviation 0.11.

	C3	failed	false	dm	CPU(min)
1.30	2	4	3.5	1.6	
1.25	2	4	3.5	1.9	
1.20	2	4	3.5	2.6	
1.15	2	2	3.8	3.7	
1.10	2	1	3.8	4.9	
1.05	2	1	3.8	8.2	
1.00	2	0	4.0	9.9	

For the 'medium' separation systems, the number of LS-iterations in the search for the secondary position could again be decreased to four, together with $C_1=75$ and $C_2=2$. Table 3 shows the solution statistics, again with steeply increasing computing-times as C_3 is decreased. The failed solution has $\epsilon_r=2.7$ arcsec, well outside the mesh-size. (One of the simulated systems had $\epsilon_p=4.1$ arcsec, and is therefore also excluded). The remaining false solution has $\Delta m=4.0$ mag and S_f as low as 0.94. It is computationally expensive to decrease C_3 that much.

Table 3. Number of failed and false solutions, completeness-limit in Δm , and mean CPU-time per system for 39 systems with separation 1-3 arcsec (single IFOV-pointing) and primary position error less than 3 arcsec. The mean normalized fit S_f is about 1.09, with standard deviation 0.09.

	C3	failed	false	dm	CPU(min)
1.30	1	6	3.3	1.4	
1.25	1	6	3.3	1.8	
1.20	1	4	3.5	2.2	
1.15	1	3	3.5	4.0	
1.10	1	2	3.7	4.6	
1.05	1	2	3.7	8.1	
1.00	1	1	3.9	9.2	

For the 'wide' systems also, 4 LS-iterations are enough, but $C_1=100$ was chosen in order to catch some difficult systems ($C_2=2$). Table 4 gives the statistics, again closely analogous to the previous ones. The failed solution is for an equal-magnitude system with large ϵ_r , where the primary-solution never even has $S_a < 100$ ($C_1=130$ gives a good solution).

Table 4. Number of failed and false solutions, completeness-limit in Δm , and mean CPU-time per system for 40 systems with separation 3-10 arcsec (single IFOV-pointing) and primary position error less than 3 arcsec. The mean normalized fit S_f is about 1.03, with standard deviation 0.12.

	C3	failed	false	dm	CPU(min)
1.30	1	3	3.2	1.6	
1.25	1	3	3.2	2.1	
1.20	1	2	3.3	2.1	
1.15	1	1	3.7	2.9	
1.10	1	0	4.0	3.8	
1.05	1	0	4.0	4.7	

4. Further tests

The above series of solutions were all made with large search-meshes for the primary and secondary (relative) positions. Although this will catch most of the possible solutions, it is more economical to envisage a processing in three separate stages, for *each* group of systems with approximately known maximum position errors.

First, we separate the stars according to Δm . The systems with small (a priori) Δm are not expected to give any false solutions, and we may therefore use a relatively large value for C_3 . Also, because most systems have much smaller a priori errors than the estimated extremes, we use in this 'stage 1' a smaller number of mesh-points. The result will be a sizeable number of solutions *plus* a number of failures in a relatively short computing-time. These failed systems are then solved in 'stage 2' with large meshes and an extra large C_1 (and C_3 still large because false solutions are not expected). The systems with large Δm are the ones where false solutions may be a problem, and these are therefore run in 'stage 3' with a small value of C_3 and large mesh-sizes. As shown above, this will take a lot of computing-time, although some improvement may result from using smaller C_1 and C_2 .

This 'hybrid' solution scheme has been tested on the above 158 simulated systems, and the results in Table 5 show that almost all systems may be solved by suitable choices of the C_i -parameters. The values chosen have a large influence on the computing-times, as may be seen from the multiple tries of the 'Stage 3'-part. (Note e.g how a decreased C_2 almost halves the computing-time for the 'medium' systems, but that it also makes one of the 'wide' solutions fail). The 'mean' CPU-time per system is given for an 'optimal' choice of the C_i :s, but it is strongly dominated by the systems with large Δm . In reality, the relative number of systems with $\Delta m > 3$ will be smaller (and the mean a priori errors smaller), thus the times given in Table 5 may be considered as upper limits.

Table 5. Solution statistics and total CPU-times for the three stages of solutions for each separation-group (close=0.3-1, med=1-3, wide=3-10 and very wide=10-30 arcsec). The number of primary and secondary mesh-points and the C-values are also given. In the last row for each group is given the total number of solutions and the *mean* CPU-time per system.

Stage	nmesh	C1	C2	C3	failed	false	OK	CPU(min)
cl(1)	61,19(1)	50.	2.0	1.30	7	0	24	32
cl(2)	169,61(19)	150.	2.0	1.30	0	0	7	40
cl(3)	169,61(19)	150.	2.0	1.00	0	0	9	141
cl(3)	169,61(19)	50.	2.0	1.00	0	0	9	124
cl(3)	169,61(19)	50.	1.5	1.00	0	0	9	105
						(close	40/40	4.4)
m(1)	61,19(1)	50.	2.0	1.30	8	0	14	33
m(2)	169,61(19)	150.	2.0	1.30	0	0	8	23
m(3)	169,61(19)	150.	2.0	1.00	0	1	15	227
m(3)	169,61(19)	50.	2.0	1.00	0	1	15	216
m(3)	169,61(19)	50.	1.5	1.00	0	1	15	115
						(medium	37/38	4.5)
w(1)	61,19(1)	50.	2.0	1.25	7	0	19	32
w(2)	169,61(19)	150.	2.0	1.25	0	0	7	9
w(3)	169,61(19)	50.	2.0	1.10	0	0	14	46
w(3)	169,61(19)	50.	1.5	1.10	1	0	13	33
						(wide	40/40	2.2)
vw(1)	61,19(1)	25.	1.8	0.95	11	0	21	73
vw(2)	169,61(19)	50.	1.8	0.95	0	0	11	118
vw(3)	169,61(19)	50.	1.8	0.85	0	0	8	219
vw(3)	169,61(19)	25.	1.8	0.85	0	0	8	206
vw(3)	169,61(19)	25.	1.2	0.85	0	0	8	176
						(very wide	40/40	9.2)

The above procedure and C_i -choices were tailored to one particular set of simulated systems. As a second test, these methods were therefore applied to another set of simulated systems. This consists of 50 'close' and 50 'wide' systems, in each case with half the Δm :s between 0 and 1 mag and half between 2.5 and 3.5 mag. A third subset of 49 'very wide' systems all had Δm :s between 2.5 and 3.5 mag. The assumed primary (1-axis) position mean error was 1 arcsec (as previously), but the mean error in the relative positions was 0.3 arcsec (against 0.7). The Δm dividing-line for Stage 1+2 versus Stage 3 solution was again taken at 3.0 magnitudes, but the secondary search-mesh was diminished (in accordance with the smaller a priori errors). The solution parameters and results are given in Table 6.

In the main, the 3-stage procedure works very well, but the C_1 and C_2 chosen influence both the computing-times and the solution statistics. (As before, the 'wide' systems show the least problems). The mean computing-times per system are smaller than before (by about a factor two), in qualitative agreement with the smaller a priori secondary errors. (As another comparison, the present 149 systems were analyzed by the 'old' STDDBL program. This gives good solutions for all (63) systems with secondary errors less than 0.33 arcsec. In the interval 0.33-0.57 arcsec, 54 out of 62 systems get good solutions, but with 0.57-0.82 arcsec secondary error, only 9 out of 24 are successful).

Table 6. Solution statistics and total CPU-times for the three stages of solutions for each separation-group in the 'old' simulations (close=0.3-1, wide=3-10 and very wide=10-30 arcsec separation). The number of primary and secondary mesh-points and the C-values are also given. In the last row for each group is given the total number of solutions and the *mean* CPU-time per system.

Stage	nmesh	C1	C2	C3	failed	false	OK	CPU(min)
cl(1)	61,7(1)	50.	2.0	1.30	5	0	30	33
cl(2)	169,19(7)	150.	2.0	1.30	0	0	5	75
cl(2)	169,19(7)	100.	2.0	1.30	0	0	5	19
cl(3)	169,19(7)	50.	1.5	1.00	1	1	13	59
cl(3)	169,19(7)	50.	2.0	1.00	0	0	15	75
						(close	50/50	2.5)
w(1)	61,7(1)	50.	2.0	1.25	3	0	36	23
w(2)	169,19(7)	150.	2.0	1.25	0	0	3	1
w(3)	169,19(7)	50.	1.5	1.10	0	0	11	5
						(wide	50/50	0.6)
vw(1)	61,7(1)	25.	1.8	0.95	4	0	20	45
vw(2)	169,19(7)	50.	1.8	0.95	0	0	4	25
vw(3)	169,19(7)	25.	1.2	0.85	0	0	25	188
						(very wide	49/49	5.3)

In the closing stages of these program-tests (after correcting some obvious bugs that luckily do not seem to have affected the solutions appreciably), I finally also realized that my routine for the normal equations accumulation calculated *all* elements of the (symmetric) matrix. A ('single character') change to do only the upper-diagonal part gave an immediate 35% decrease in the total computing-times. Further optimization of the code is not likely to be as dramatic, but there is probably a potential for improvement.

5. Conclusions

As shown above, the large majority of known doubles may be solved by the new STDDDBLS program with its search for the primary *and* secondary positions. The number of mesh-points that has to be tried increases (at least) quadratically with the a priori errors, but in principle, very large search-meshes may be tried for a smaller number of difficult systems. The 'typical' mean computing-times are difficult to estimate (because they depend sensitively on the actual distribution of a priori errors and magnitude differences), but they are of the order of a few minutes for the HP9000/835 computer. (With the old HP9000/500 system, the times would have been ten times longer and the STDDDBLS program could hardly have been contemplated for a majority of the 11000 known doubles).

Although the tolerance for errors in the relative positions is even smaller for multiples, an 'upgrading' of STDMUL along the lines of STDDDBLS is *not* feasible. The computing-times and the logics of a multi-mesh search would be prohibitive, and it is imperative instead to make further ground-based observations of these systems. Only when a priori relative positions within 0.1 or 0.2 arcsec are available will it be possible to analyze the HIPPARCOS observations of multiple systems properly.